

NEUROFILAMENT LIGHT CHAIN MEASUREMENT WITH ELECTROCHEMILUMINESCENCE METHOD (NFL-ECL) IN CEREBROSPINAL FLUID AS PROMISING DIAGNOSTIC METHOD OF AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is an autoimmune-based neurodegenerative disease which signed with degeneration of upper motor neuron (UMN) and lower motor neuron (LMN), considered as one of neurodegenerative disease with high morbidity and mortality rate. To date, there is no appropriate diagnostic method could detect ALS during early onset, which aimed to maximize and efficient the success rate of therapy. Neurofilament Light Chain (NFL) is a component of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) which regulate axon diameter calibration and conduction speed in action potential of neurons. Several studies have shown that NFL concentration in CSF could be used to measure ALS severity based on its role in ALS pathogenesis. Electrochemiluminescence (ECL) is one of the current methods that could be used in measuring NFL with high sensitivity rate and affordable price. In this review, the author proposed NFL measurement with ECL method (NFL-ECL) as a current ALS diagnostic modality. In this review, several literatures were analyzed and synthesized. From 29 journals that have been included in criteria, only 23 of them were used in this review. Used journals are paper journals or e-journals that obtained from Google Scholar, BMJ Journals, The Lancet, PubMed, and other valid and accredited online journal bases. Results have shown that NFL measurement with ECL method has 97% sensitivity rate for prognostic diagnosis and 86-94% sensitivity rate for early-onset diagnosis. In conclusion, CSF based NFL measurement with ECL is a promising method for diagnosing ALS.

KEYWORDS Neurofilament Light Chain, Electrochemiluminescence, Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, Diagnostic

Background

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is one of neurodegenerative disease which classified as autoimmune-related with upper motor neuron (UMN) and lower motor neuron (LMN) degeneration.[1] In the United States, ALS was widely known as Lou Gehrig's disease.[2] Advance in ALS understanding accordance to glutamate neurotransmitter and gene discovery in familial ALS has been increasing research interest in observing ALS and its diagnostic approaches.[3]

Globally, ALS prevalence is unknown in detail, but it has

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been found that ALS incident is higher in male (3 in 100.000 people/year) compared to female (2,4 in 100.000 people/year). ALS onset usually happened within 58-63 years old (sporadic ALS) and 47-52 years old (familial ALS).[3] According to research by Okumiya et al., ALS prevalence in Indonesia is higher than the global average, where it was found in Papua (Irian Jaya). There are 46 cases with ALS and/or Parkinson diagnosis in a population of 7000 (2001-2002) until 13.900 people (2007-2012). Based on these cases, 17 examples are found to be definite ALS and 13 others with overlapping symptoms.[4] More than 60% of ALS patients could not survive within 3 years from the first onset, and 10% of patients survived more than 8 years.[2]

To alleviate ALS patients life expectancy, it depends on an understanding of ALS pathogenesis itself. With understanding ALS pathogenesis it will lead to earlier, better, and more specific diagnosis, including the development of new methods to diagnose this disease. There is an urgent and essential need in ALS therapy, not only in suppressing developing signs and severity, but also considering the possible complication that could worsen patient's condition. Therefore, early diagnosis is an important thing to increase ALS therapy success rate.[3]

Early clinical symptoms of ALS are progressive neurological deteriorations, majorly present as limb symptoms (65%), bulbar dysfunction (30%) in dysarthria or dysphagia form, and respiratory problem (5%). Decrease in body weight and emotional instability also been reported as the early symptoms of ALS. These symptoms are also involving corticospinal tract, brain stem, and motor neurons in medulla spinalis. Clinical manifestations and progression of ALS are varied and causing indefinite diagnosis, as the onset of ALS take 9 to 15 months and would take two until three specialists to conclude a definite diagnosis of ALS.[2] Clinical symptoms caused by ALS might overlap with another neurodegenerative disease. This would create difficulties and uncertainty in ALS diagnosis. Current diagnostic methods only depend and limited to signs; therefore the sensitivity is very low.[3] Based on the background, there is a need for a new diagnostic method with high sensitivity to maximize certainty in diagnosing ALS and diagnosis could be done earlier.

Neurofilament Light Chain (NFL) is a component of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and have a high probability as a biomarker to diagnose ALS, looking in its significant increase in ALS patient.[1] A study review of cytoskeleton components such as tau protein, neurofilament, and S100 as an indicator of ALS progression. Cytoskeleton components are observed in transgenic mice, whereas neurofilament was found as a significant intermediate filament in neuron cytoskeleton. According to a research conducted by Tortelli et al., measurement of NFL in CSF to diagnose ALS has higher sensitivity and specificity if compared to previous diagnostic methods.[5]

By this review, authors would introduce to a current diagnostic approach to measure NFL with electrochemiluminescence method (NFL-ECL) with CSF base to diagnose ALS, whereas ECL has high sensitivity and affordable price. Through this review, will be explained eminence of this biomarker compared to the standard diagnostic method of ALS.

Review Method

Twenty-nine journals were selected, and 23 of them were reviewed. Journals used in this paper were selected from various accredited and online-based sources, such as Google Scholar, BMJ, The Lancet, and PubMed. Keywords used for searching the literatures were "Neuro Filament Light Chain", "diagnosis",

"Electrochemiluminescence", "Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis", "Predictive factor", "sensitivity", and "specificity".

Neurofilament Light Chain Roles in Neuronal Physiology

Cytoskeleton in the nervous system is composed of three major components – microfilament, intermediate filament, and microtubule – that build major part and shape of the neuron. Neurofilament (NF) is a major intermediate filament in the nervous system and its expression is regulated by the type neuron. The primary function of NF is axonal calibration on myelinated axon and function as axon conduction speed regulator. NF also take a role in neuron development as it differentiates, grows, and regenerates. There are three major protein components that build NF; NFL, NF medium chain (NFM), NF heavy chain (NFH). These components consist of three domain – head domain, rod domain and tail domain – where each domain has a role in components binding. [6,9] Recent study has found that there is the fourth component to build NF; alpha-Internexin to build NF in the central nervous system (CNS), peripherin to build NF in the peripheral nervous system (PNS). Therefore, regulation in NF synthesis from its component is an important role in the development of human nervous system.[6,7,8,9]

NFL has a crucial role in NF formation. Several studies have shown that NFM and NFH availability would not assemble into NF without NFL presence. But, NFL can create its own homopolymer and synthesize NF. NF assembly process begins with NFL dimerization and bondage with NFM and NFH and creating a parallel dimer, become tetramer, and progressing become mature filament. NFL functions as the binding center of NFM and NFH in NF synthesis. [9]

NF assembly regulation is very important and correlated with each component of NF expression. NFL is expressed by NEFL gene, NFM is expressed by NEFM gene, and NFH is expressed by NEFH gene. According to a study that conducted in mice, a mutation in NFL mRNA would lead to shrunken axon diameter and decrease in NFM synthesis. This study showed that NFL expression affects NFM expression in myelinated axon calibration and affect neuron conduction speed.[9,10] NF regulation is done through several post-translation modifications, for example, NFL head-rod domain phosphorylation. Phosphorylated filament could not attach to another filament and assemble as mature NF. This regulation is done to avoid NF overaccumulation in the improper site of the axon and would cause shrinking in axon diameter. As been told before, NF assembly is regulated by neuron type and length. This mechanism is regulated by axonal transport toward axon target location that will calibrate and widened. If there is any failure in axonal transport, it would cause NF continuous synthesis and accumulated in improper site and would cause pathological condition. [11,12]

Neurofilament Light Chain in ALS Pathogenesis

One of the mechanisms that should be owned by NF is regulation. If there any misregulation in NF synthesis, it would lead to pathological condition in neuron. In ALS, researcher suspect that excessive aggregation of NF in motoneuron is the main cause of ALS pathological condition. There are several things that would trigger this condition.[9]

NFL overexpression would lead to excessive aggregation. Studies have shown that overexpression of another monomer – NFM, NFH – could be suppressed by high synthesis of NFL, and vice versa. But mentioned before that NFM and NFH expression is affected by NFL expression.[6,12] Therefore, NEFL mutation

is susceptible as the main risk factor of ALS pathogenesis, triggering excessive aggregation in motoneuron and perikaryon, causing motoneuron degeneration, axon atrophy and leading to severe atrophy of skeletal muscle. Decrease in NFL mRNA transcription also predicted as a trigger for ALS.[9,11]

Inadequate phosphorylation in NF component also susceptible as ALS pathogenesis cause. As mentioned before, phosphorylation maintain NF components detached to another component in its transport to axon target site. Any flaw in this phosphorylation mechanism that causing inadequate phosphorylation, mainly in NFL and NFM, these components will be easily bonding one each other and aggregate in improper site. Study has shown that mutation in codon that encode NF component phosphorylation would cause excessive phosphorylation and become the main key of ALS sporadic cases.[9,10]

Superoxide dismutase-1 gene (SOD1) mutation is also susceptible as the main cause of ALS. In a trial using SOD1 mutant mice, these mice showing similar ALS symptoms with another group with NFL overexpression. Researchers suspect that SOD1 has role in NF axonal transport regulation. Researchers found that SOD1 take action of NF axonal transport with perturbation.[9,11,12] But the perturbation mechanism remains unknown until now. Recent study only found that SOD1 mutation would lead to NF aggregation in motoneuron, but the concentration between NFL concentration and SOD1 are independent variables.[11,12]

Common Diagnostic Methods for Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis

Until this time, there is no effective method of ALS diagnostic. ALS diagnosis still using El Escorial criteria, created in the year 1990 and revised in Airlie house in 1999. These diagnostic criteria are made according to UMN and LMN symptoms identification, which found from neurologic examination and ALS progression. The diagnosis could be definite on later phase, but in the early phase, misdiagnosis often happens. Therefore, early and accurate is needed for patient and healthcare professionals to plan therapy and further management. Mistakes also could be found due to ALS clinical symptoms heterogeneity. [13] Electromyography and other electrodiagnostic methods could increase diagnostic sensitivity. Lambert criteria based on EMG also merged with revised El Escorial criteria, but nowadays these criteria are found to be less sensitive and incomplete.[14] There is also Awaji criteria. According to a study, Awaji criteria has shown sensitivity increase in diagnosis in the Chinese population, compared to revised El Escorial criteria. Awaji criteria have 78% sensitivity, while revises El Escorial criteria has 36% sensitivity ($p < 0.001$).[15] Neuroimaging using PET scan, fMRI, DTI, and MRS also showing no significant high sensitivity or specificity.[16]

NFL as A Diagnostic Biomarker

NF will be released in certain whether axonal damage or neuron degeneration is present. If there any damage in axonal membrane NF will be released in interstitial fluid, and then CSF, and could be found in blood.[17] NF concentration also has correlation with several regions (bulbar, upper limb, lower limb) and UMN and LMN involvement, and on regions that involved LMN on EMG according to revised El Escorial criteria or Awaji criteria.[18] NFL is the most abundant subunit in body and easily diluted. Several studies have shown that NFH and NFL presence in CSF is assumed to have compatibility with brain

pathologic condition compared to peripheral blood sample, even CSF drawing considered to be a procedure that is more invasive. [17]

CSF drawing is conducted through lumbar puncture, processed to aliquot in a polypropylene tube and stored by temperature -80°C . Examination could be done through two methods, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and electrochemoluminescence (ECL). [17,19] NFL-ECL examination protocol by Gaiottino et al. proved to be very accurate (intra-assay CV $< 6\%$, interassay CV $< 24\%$), sensitive (sensitivity cutoff value : 15,6 pg/mL), and shown linearly and parallel with wide analytic area (15,6 pg - 10.000 pg/mL).[17] "Hook effect" that potentially lead to inconsistent result and often to be found in NFH measurement, is nowhere to be found in NFL measurement.[20]

On the same study, Gaiottino et al. examine CSF from 224 patients – 67 healthy patients, 68 control patients (CP), 20 Alzheimer's Disease (AD) patients, Guillain -Barré Syndrome (GBS), Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) – found that average CSF sample (1.142 pg/mL, 906-1.439) compared to peripheral blood sample (11.8 pg/mL, 8,5-16,5) has NFL concentration 96.8 times higher (CP = 73.6; GBS = 17.1; ALS = 57.8; $p < 0,0001$). From three populations with disease, NFL measurement has higher significance in detecting and differentiate ALS from other disease (ALS vs. GBS $p < 0,0001$; ALS vs. AD $p < 0,0001$).[17]

NFL concentration on CSF and serum have a high correlation (ALS: $r = 0,78$; $p < 0,0001$; control : $r = 0,57$; $p = 0,008$) and the concentration found 73.8 times higher in ALS and 34.6 times higher compared to control.[20]

According to research by Lu et al., NFL in CSF has high sensitivity and specificity to detect ALS prognosis, by 97% and 95% on cut-off level by 1781 pg/mL (AUC = 0,9987, $p < 0,0001$).[20] NFL-ECL also to be proved well to diagnose and measure ALS severity on early phase with high sensitivity and specificity – 94% sensitivity and 86% specificity (AUC 0,95, cut-off 2.300 pg/mL), by 89% sensitivity and 94% specificity (AUC 0,94, cut-off 2.183 pg/mL).[19]

Level of Log[NFL] also has correlation with patients survival rate (HR, 2,45; 95% CI, 1, 66-3,61; $p < 0,001$) and could be used as prognosis indicator of disease progression based on Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis Functional Rating-Score Revised (ALSFRS-R) and Milano-Torino Staging. NFL concentration also inversely proportional with the duration of disease progression. Therefore, patients with higher NFL would develop more severe phase, while patients with rapid onset, have higher NFL concentration, would come and plan treatment earlier.[21]

From those results could be concluded that NFL in CSF has correlation with ALS patients and could be used as a biomarker to diagnose early onset of ALS. Increased NFL level in CSF also could be concluded to detect probability in ALS.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Neurofilament Light Chain as Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis Biomarker

NFL is still not approved and validated by FDA. This procedure needs to be standardized to diminish bias result caused by pre-analytic and analytic factors. Also, the stability of NF concentration in CSF is still debatable, where a study mentioned that NFL concentration is stable whenever stored in room temperature for several days, through several freeze-thaw cycle, and minimal contamination by blood (0.05%). But other studies also mentioned that NFL concentration could decrease rapidly in CSF.[22]

CSF drawing using lumbar puncture also considered as an

invasive method and may cause discomfort to patient. But biomarker diagnosis using CSF sample has better prospect and predictive value for early diagnosis, due to its high sensitivity and specificity trait compared to other methods. A better understanding towards NFL release as pathologic response, exclusively in pre-symptomatic period or factor that could alleviate pathological process of the diagnosis would confirm the diagnosis and increasing therapy success with this method.[20]

Analysis of Potency and Applicability

Diagnostic trials measuring NFL concentration with ECL method have shown a lot of benefits in ALS early diagnosis. Besides its high sensitivity and specificity, NFL concentration measurement could unfold other information that would diagnose thoroughly from UMN and LMN signs. With ECL proper use, it is expected that practitioners that able to implement this method would be able to examine and decide patients' prognosis and plan a better therapy for the patients according to the acquired information. In Indonesia, ECL has been implemented as a diagnostic kit for some diseases but hasn't been applied to diagnose ALS. ECL is a method with high sensitivity from luminescence method group with an affordable price, using cloth-based devices method which cost around USD 0.015 (approximately IDR 209.5). Report from Zhang et al., wax screen printing is used to pattern the hydrophobic and hydrophilic on 60-90 mm width cotton cloth. Then, carbon electrodes are screen-printed and form electrochemical cells. These electrodes have cyclic voltammogram on 5 mm diameter carbon that functions as electrode and ECL is built with luminol/hydrogen peroxide and $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ /TPPrA ECL system. Other methods that could be done is planar paper-based microfluidic devices with same advantages and benefits but with a slightly higher price (USD 0.80, approximately IDR 11,280). There is also 3D Origami Microfluidic Devices method, but it takes longer fabrication time compared to paper-based devices method.[23]

Conclusion and Suggestions

Measurement of NFL in CSF with ECL method could be a promising accurate diagnostic method with a high sensitivity and specificity. Although this method could be more invasive, it could serve better information compared to other diagnostic methods. This method could explain and widened better understanding in patients early onset diagnosis, prognosis, life expectancy, etc. The cost of this ECL method is affordable, and expected would be able to suppress number of ALS cases in the future. This novel method also hoped to provide better information to diagnose, which lead to a better therapy plan for the patient. FDA is expected to do further examination in approving this method as a promising diagnostic method. Additional researchers need to be conducted so that this method could be applied in the future clinical situation.

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Conflict of Interest

At this moment, authors declared that through the process of this review was independent of conflict of interest that would lead to bias in this review.

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